

A STUDY ON WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF MARRIED WOMEN IN BPOs OF BANGALORE CITY AND ITS IMPACT ON JOB SATISFACTION

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ABSTRACT

The work-life balance among married women in the BPO sector remains a critical issue and requires concerted efforts from both employees and employers. By addressing the unique challenges women face through flexible work arrangements, strong support systems, and organizational policies, a more equitable and sustainable work environment can be achieved. Ultimately, fostering work-life balance not only benefits individual employees but also enhances the overall productivity and job satisfaction within the BPO industry. The main objectives of the present research are to find out the impact of personal factors of married women and organizational factors on job satisfaction of married women working in BPOs in Bangalore city. Both primary and secondary data were collected for the study purpose. The questionnaires were issued to the chosen respondents (married women) with the help of the human resource managers of the respective BPO companies. There were 485 respondents selected from different BPOs in the entire Bangalore city. The random sampling was carried out keeping in view that the respondents selected are representative of the sample and are distributed evenly. Linear regression was used to find out the impact on job satisfaction with the help of SPSS software. The research revealed that both personal factors of married women and organizational factors are significantly impacting the job satisfaction of married women working in the BPO sector in the Bangalore city.

Key words: Work Life Balance, Married Women, BPO, Personal Factors, Organizational Factors, Job Satisfaction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In earlier days the contribution of a woman was restricted only to her home and family, but now, crossing the thorny boundaries of the society, women have ventured into corporate. The growth of education and awareness has led women to work in industries and corporations. "Women are not only the backbone of nuclear and joint families but also the national

economy.” Women have started venturing into areas that were seen as dominated by men. Women in all fields have proved their excellence and skills. Women have proved their commitment and versatility for ages and have also carried different roles successfully. In recent times, the issue of work-life balance has gained more attention due to the reason that an individual's work life and personal life may present conflicting demands on one another while the demands from both spheres are equally important (Dhallam, S., & Dhawan, R. 2019). Work-life balance refers to maintaining the balance between performing roles and responsibilities at work and at home (Varalakshmi, C., et al., 2023). Work-life balance is one of the most challenging issues being faced by the women employees in the 21st century (Amirtha Rajan et al., 2020). This problem is more for women employees because of the type of roles they play at home and the spillover of personal life over work life and vice versa (Janani, R. 2021).

2. WORK-LIFE BALANCE

Work-life balance, as a concept, stresses the efforts taken by the employees to divide their time and energy between work and the other important aspects of their lives (Salvi, C. 2022). It also signifies the efforts taken by people to share time with their families, friends, and community and give importance to various aspects of their lives, such as spirituality, personal growth, self-care, and other personal activities, over and above their efforts in meeting the demands of the workplace (Sivakumar et al., 2015). During the 1980s men also began voicing work-life concerns. By the end of the decade, work-life balance was seen as more than just a women's issue, affecting men, families, organizations, and cultures (Kumari, T. K., 2015). During the first years of the twenty-first century, the disappointing results made human resource and work-life professionals as well as executives at all levels take stock (Chockalingam, S. M., & Sudarshan, P. 2018). This aims at encouraging employers to adopt flexible working arrangements such as job sharing, flexitime, compressed hours, and others to help their employees to achieve a better balance between the demands of paid employment and those arising from their private life (Raajarajeswari, M. A., & Saravanan, R. 2015). The perception of work-life balance is based on the notion that paid work and personal life should be seen less as competing priorities than as complementary elements of a full life (Mohanasoundari, R., & Indhumathi, K., 2024). The technique to achieve this is to embrace an approach that is “conceptualized as a two-way process involving a consideration of the needs of employees as well as those of employers” (Santhiya, S 2021). In order to include employers in this practice, it is important to validate the benefits that can be derived from employment policies and practices that support work-life balance (Brindha A. & Premkumar, M. D. 2025). Efraty and Sirgy conducted research on the impact of work-life balance on employee replies in 1988 (Vanitha, A. 2022). They discovered that job happiness, organizational identity, job participation, and job performance are all positively associated with work-life balance (Bavya M.P. & Raghunandan M.V., 2018). They also discovered that poor work-life balance contributes to employee alienation. The following are some major aspects that influence work-life balance. Work satisfaction is the degree to which an employee is self-motivated, fulfilled, and pleased with his or her employment (Valk, R., & Srinivasan, V. 2011). Workers that have

a great quality of life at work have higher levels of job satisfaction. Job participation—the degree to which a person is emotionally and mentally invested in his or her job (Jain, A., & Dhingra, V. 2022). It has been discovered that top achievers in organizations have a greater level of job participation (Ariya S & Sarun S. G. 2024). Work-life balance is closely associated with job participation, implying that a good work-life balance leads to a high level of job involvement (Parmar, M. N. & Rajshekhar, J. 2010). Organizational identification is the degree to which employees believe they are one with the organization or describe themselves as members of the organization (Sengupta, N. & Sengupta, M., 2017). Work performance—An employee who has a great work-life balance performs better on the job. Greater job participation and job satisfaction lead to improved performance (Soumya, S. 2022). Organizational performance—An improvement in individual employee performance leads to an increase in overall organizational performance (Kumaraswamy, M., & Ashwini, S. 2015). Absenteeism and turnover are reduced—it has been found that employees who have a great work-life balance at work have a lower rate of absenteeism (Tanwar, J. 2018). Attrition rates in such organizations are also lower than the industry average. Given the foregoing, any researcher would be interested in researching the quality of work life (Balamurugan, G., & Sreeleka, M. 2020). Scholars in this discipline have undertaken several studies. The next chapter, which is based on a survey of literature on work-life balance, provides an overview of such research (Manoharan, G. & Ashtikar, S. P., 2023). Women of this era are strongly career-oriented. Moreover, managing household and office work demands more time, commitment, focus, and the like (Yogeshwaran, P. 2016). These requisites result in role stressors. Hence, this study primarily focused attention only on the phenomena of role conflict, role ambiguity, and role overload among women BPO employees in Bengaluru District (Kumar, R. M. 2021).

3. BUSINESS PROCESS OUTSOURCING (BPO) INDUSTRY

The Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industry in India is one of the fastest-growing sectors and a major contributor to the country's economy (Singhal, D., N., & Maheshwari, N. 2014). It involves outsourcing various business processes, such as customer support, finance and accounting, human resources, and IT services, to third-party service providers. India's BPO industry has flourished due to several factors, including a large English-speaking workforce, cost-effective services, advanced technology infrastructure, and government support (Sandhya M. & Prabhu P. D., 2022). Women make up a substantial portion of the workforce in India's BPO sector. Estimates suggest that women constitute about 30-35% of the total employees in the industry (Dhallam, S., & Dhawan, R. 2019). This percentage has been gradually increasing over the years as more women enter the workforce and seek career opportunities in the growing BPO sector. The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of remote work in the BPO industry, which has had mixed effects on married women employees (Varalakshmi, C., et al., 2023). On one hand, remote work has provided greater flexibility, allowing women to better manage their work and family responsibilities (Amirtha Rajan et al., 2020). On the other hand, it has also blurred the lines between work and home life, making it challenging for many to maintain a healthy work-life balance (Janani, R. 2021). In Bengaluru, the workforce participation of women in the BPO sector and other industries has been growing, with a significant presence in manufacturing (Das, S. S., et al., 2016). Specifically, Bengaluru

accounts for over 40% of India's female workforce in manufacturing sectors, including BPOs. While exact percentages of married vs. unmarried women in the BPO sector in Bengaluru aren't readily available, the state's overall emphasis on gender diversity suggests a balanced workforce across different sectors, with support systems to encourage women's participation, regardless of marital status (Ragothaman, C. B., & Chitra, R. N., 2021).

4. JOB SATISFACTION

Sundaresan (2014) finds in his study that there is a direct connection between job satisfaction and work-life balance. In the initial stages of a job, it is very necessary to know how jobs make employees feel comfortable, but in the later stages, in case it is found that employees get fed up with their monotonous work and look out for a strong change in work schedule, it is clear that they need a change (Balamurugan, G., & Sreeleka, M. 2020). (Chandrasekaran, M., et al., 2009) Found that ladies' employees experienced serious anxiety during the time spent achieving work-life balance. Women proceeded with work, and weight led to poor execution of given assignments (Manorama, Singhal, N., 2024). The outcome uncovered that numerous female instructors have ignored their well-being during the time spent (Suresh P. A. & Kumari, A., 2022). Job satisfaction is one of the most popular and widely researched topics in the field of organizational psychology, which defines job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences (Muniyappa, B., 2019). Job satisfaction has been studied both as a consequence of many individual and work environments. In the recent past, the Indian BPO sector has undergone significant developments and investments. Job satisfaction is the difference between what married women employees expected to experience and what they received from their job (Huda, M.S. 2024). Indeed, a worker with low expectations may be more satisfied with his or her job than one with high expectations. One is happy and satisfied if the job meets or exceeds one's expectations (Manorama & Singhal, N 2024). Job satisfaction refers to an individual's positive attitude about the work position that he is now occupying, as well as the pleasant feeling state that results from the appraisal of one's job as accomplishing or facilitating one's worth (Reena & Jain, 2024). Job satisfaction can also be defined as a positive attitude toward one's job, as well as a set of sentiments and beliefs that span the mental, emotional, and physical realms (Abiramivikashini, A. 2023). Job satisfaction is also defined as an employee's emotional response to a variety of job-related aspects that results in pleasure, comfort, confidence, rewards, personal advancement, and other opportunities, including upward mobility, recognition, and merit-based assessment with monetary remuneration (Kohili, P., 2017). Job satisfaction can also be defined as an employee's overall emotional assessment of himself or herself in relation to his or her work. Job satisfaction is a goal that many employees strive for but few achieve (Suresh P. A. & Kumari, A., 2022). Organizations must understand the factors contributing to employee happiness and how they affect company performance. Job satisfaction is a feeling that can have a positive or negative impact on one's job functions and responsibilities (Manorama, Singhal, N., 2024).

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

The regression study indicated how human resource practices may be encouraged with staff motivation, its influence on productivity, and the daily issues of the BPO business in managing

the WLB for female workers (Kohili, P., 2017). The study of the relationship between shift work and work-life conflict, life-work conflict, psychosomatic diseases, and turnover intentions. According to the study's results, respondents who worked nonstandard working hours (second shift and night shift) had a better work-life balance (Abiramivikashini, A. 2023). Work-life conflict was found to be low for respondents working second shifts, and the frequency of psychosomatic diseases was low for respondents working night shifts (Reena & Jain, 2024). The conflict from work to family responsibilities indirectly influenced the conflict from family to work responsibilities by causing an increase in parental burden (Manorama & Singhal, N 2024). There are four factors relating to women's career continuity, including household responsibilities, the women's personality variables, financial considerations, and the husband's attitude towards his wife's paid employment (Huda, M.S. 2024). (Muniyappa, B., 2019) Suggested that married women in BPOs are often expected to perform the majority of domestic duties despite their professional commitments. This dual role expectation leads to role conflict, reducing their ability to fulfill both professional and personal responsibilities effectively (Salvi, C. 2022). The strain of managing both work and home life can lead to serious health concerns, such as chronic stress, anxiety, and burnout (Sivakumar et al., 2015). Health issues are exacerbated by a lack of time for physical activities, poor diet, and inadequate rest (Kumari, T. K., 2015). Work-life balance increases the motivation of employees and helps them to perform better at their jobs. It helps people to relieve their stress as they can spend leisure time with their friends and family (Chockalingam, S. M., & Sudarshan, P. 2018). Companies can maximize productivity from an employee who is rejuvenated and refreshed as compared to an overworked employee. A healthy lifestyle can be maintained by having a work-life balance (Raajarajeswari, M. A., & Saravanan, R. 2015). This includes a good diet, regular exercise, time management, etc. Employees who are highly motivated can help the business grow, as they are more attached to their jobs and careers (Mohanasoundari, R., & Indhumathi, K., 2024). Various demographic variables (age, marital status, children, and educational qualification) were found to have a major impact on the various components of work-life balance (social needs, personal needs, time management, teamwork, compensation and benefits, and work) (Santhiya, S 2021). The participation of women has also raised the challenges to balance between responsibilities of paid work and family life, as there is barely a time when there isn't any struggle. As the years have passed, the societal framework for women has also been newly designed. Though the change is but slow, women are more liberated, and the role of women has undergone changes. However, there are instances when the safety and security of women in the workplace can be questioned. The role of social support has consistently emerged in literature as an important factor that influences worker-family balance in a positive manner (Brindhya A. & Premkumar, M. D. 2025). Social support outside of work, labelled by Vanitha, A. (2022) as personal social support, may come from an employee's spouse or partner, parents, siblings, children, extended family, and friends. Numerous studies have demonstrated that personal social support is positively associated with work and family balance (Bavya M.P. & Raghunandan M.V., 2018). The role of workplace support, i.e., the support received from supervisors and co-workers, is another critical element of work and family balance (Valk, R., & Srinivasan, V. 2011). Jain, A., & Dhingra, V. (2022) found that organizational and supervisor understanding of family duties are positively related

to satisfaction with the balance between work and family life. Research shows that flexible work arrangements allow individuals to integrate work and family responsibilities in time and space and are instrumental in achieving a healthy work and family balance (Ariya S & Sarun S. G. 2024). Literature on female software workers clearly demonstrates that women experience a sense of empowerment from their work (Parmar, M. N. & Rajshekhar, J. 2010). Women working in BPOs are known to derive their identity from their occupation. Many women value their careers and their development as central concepts of their identity (Sengupta, N. & Sengupta, M., 2017). Married women employees reported that they face difficulties in maintaining a balance between work and family, and their careers suffer because of family responsibility (Soumya, S. 2022). A reason for this difficulty is likely to be the lack of help from their husbands. A survey conducted by Kumaraswamy, M., & Ashwini, S. (2015) indicated that only 34% of husbands extended help willingly to their wives. 22% of husbands sometimes helped out, but a large proportion still subscribed to the traditional role and did not extend help to their wives. Tanwar (2018) found that motherhood makes balancing difficult because women have to manage the external interfaces of work and career and the management of home and children (Balamurugan & Sreeleka, 2020). It must be recognized that in Indian society, where a woman's role in relation to herself, her family, and society is being redefined, the new and expanded role of women with a strong occupational identity is putting a lot of pressure on women's time and energy (Manoharan, G. & Ashtikar, S. P., 2023). The study revealed that long and irregular work hours, traveling distance between home and workplace, and commitment to other official tasks were deemed the most workplace problems (Yogeshwaran, P. 2016). The majority of married women employees depend on social media connections to get rid of work stress, but at the same time, they are more concerned about their elders at home. Most women would prefer flexible scheduling, a supportive spouse, family, and an office setting that promotes productivity (Kumar, R. M. 2021). A number of individual variables, viz., gender, age, marital status, and those related to work-life balance/work-family conflict, have been investigated by different scholars. Family-related variables such as spouse support, spouse work hours, couple's employment status, number of children, parental responsibilities, and home responsibilities have been investigated in relation to work-life balance/conflict (Singhal, D. N., & Maheshwari, N. 2014). Relationships between work-related variables, viz., task variety, task autonomy, task complexity, role conflict, work schedule flexibility, number of hours worked, and work-life balance/work-family conflict, have been investigated (Sandhya M. & Prabhu P. D., 2022).

6. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Women's careers are now constantly challenged by changing workplace expectations. After work, they will have obligations and commitments at home. The majority of working women are stretched to fulfill their roles at work and at home, resulting in work-life imbalance, which has negative consequences for both individuals and organizations, such as increased stress, depression, mental health issues, family conflicts, decreased life satisfaction, etc. The business process outsourcing (BPO) industry is growing constantly in India. BPO has created numerous job avenues in the Indian workforce, as in many developing countries. In this booming sector, women play a very crucial role. Women are a key and vital part of the BPO workforce.

Bengaluru city is known as the ‘Silicon Valley of India.’ The name signifies Bengaluru as a hub for information technology companies in India. Since IT is the major industry, the existence of BPO is inevitable. Work-life balance is a contemporary issue that is gaining increasing attention from all the researchers and is at the forefront of the discussions. Changes in the workforce demographics and Western work culture in the field of communication and information technology are some of the factors that influence work-life balance. To provide a better understanding of the work-life balance of married women employees in the IT and BPO industries, the present research has been taken up to find out the factors leading to married women employees’ job satisfaction in the BPO sector.

7. NEED FOR THE STUDY

Women have played a pivotal role in shaping societies across the globe, contributing significantly to all aspects of life—economic, cultural, social, and political. Throughout history, they have shown resilience, strength, and adaptability in the face of numerous challenges. Work-life balance for the married women in the BPO sector is becoming a rising problem. Despite the persistent struggles against inequality and discrimination, women continue to break barriers, advance in various fields, and advocate for change. Their contributions are not only essential to the progress of families and communities but also to the broader advancement of humanity. Empowering women is crucial for achieving a just and equitable world. A woman employee's work-life balance has a significant influence on her behavior and performance, leading to job satisfaction in the organization. Much research has established a link between a work-life balance and specific job-related characteristics such as job satisfaction and productivity, etc. In the present scenario, due to many changes happening in the workplace and family systems, a vast majority of women are finding it difficult to achieve a desired work-life balance. In comparison with men, women have more responsibilities at home. Though there are studies on work-life balance, relatively there are fewer studies on the work-life balance of married women employees and factors leading to job satisfaction. The studies were more confined to sectors like IT/BPO. Therefore, there is a need to study how married women are balancing their work and family life in BPO sectors in the Bangalore city.

8. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the significant impact of personal factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.
2. To examine the significant impact of organizational factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.
3. To provide suitable suggestions for the improvement of job satisfaction of married women working in BPO in Bangalore city.

9. HYPOTHESIS

H0: There is no significant impact of personal factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

H1: There is a significant impact of personal factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

H0: There is no significant impact of organizational factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

H2: There is a significant impact of organizational factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

10. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is empirical research based on the survey method, and both primary and secondary data were collected. The secondary data was drawn from available literature in the field of knowledge. Primary data was collected with the help of a questionnaire prepared based on the objectives listed in the study. The questionnaires were issued to the chosen respondents (married women) with the help of the human resource managers of the respective BPO companies. This questionnaire includes personal factors and organizational factors leading to job satisfaction of married women BPO employees. The questionnaire was carefully designed, pretested, and finalized. The "5-point Likert scale" was included in a structured questionnaire that was created to collect the data. The interview was semi-structured and included open-ended conversation in Kannada, the state of Karnataka's official language. There were 485 respondents selected from different BPOs in the entire Bangalore city. The random sampling was carried out keeping in view that the respondents selected are representative of the sample and are distributed evenly. The purpose of this sample was that the number of BPO was not known, and it was difficult to find them due to their locations. However, it was kept in mind that the number of respondents should not be more than 40 (forty) from a particular organization. Further, it was difficult to get the total strength of the employees in a particular organization, and hence the total employee strength was not considered.

11. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study is confined to married women employees working in the BPO sector in Bengaluru. This study sheds light upon the factors causing job satisfaction of married women employees working in BPOs in Bengaluru. The present study covers the personal factors of married women working in BPOs, such as husband attitude, household responsibilities, supervisory and technical competences, careers and their development as central concepts, traveling distance, number of children, healthy lifestyle, professional commitments, women's demographic characteristics, ability to nurture balance between individual and organizational physical health and personality skills, parental support, etc. Organizational factors such as job security, flexible time schedule, management/policy/workplace support, task autonomy/work-role expectations, human resource practices, financial considerations, leave and benefits, safety and security of women, change in work patterns, reduction of working time, family support initiatives, and freedom to work from home were the constructs taken for the study to find out their impact on the job satisfaction of married women employees working in the BPO sector.

12. DATA ANALYSIS

The personal factors and organizational factors dimensions were analyzed based on the linear regression analysis. The collected data was duly edited and coded. Then the coded data was fed into the SPSS package, and they were put forth for analysis. SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) is a comprehensive statistical software package that was used for analyzing data.

Table 1: Personal factors and job satisfaction of married women working in BPO

H0: There is no significant impact of personal factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

H1: There is a significant impact of personal factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square		Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.896 ^a	.802	.797		.62039	
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	736.590	12	61.383	159.483	.000 ^a
	Residual	181.665	472	.385		
	Total	918.256	484			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.108	.078		1.372	.171
	Husband attitude	-.064	.068	-.066	-.936	.350
	Household responsibilities	-.019	.100	-.019	-.188	.851
	Supervisory and technical competences	.136	.110	.131	1.232	.219
	Careers and their development as central concepts	.338	.094	.340	3.582	.000
	Traveling distance	.193	.076	.192	2.548	.011
	Number of children	.084	.102	.083	.817	.414
	Healthy lifestyle	.528	.116	.532	4.544	.000
	Professional commitments	-.240	.082	-.241	-2.925	.004
	Women's demographic characteristics	.259	.087	.256	2.985	.003
	Ability of nurturing balance between individual and organizational	-.169	.071	-.173	-2.367	.018
	Physical health and personality skills	-.289	.082	-.288	-3.506	.000
	Parental support	.197	.032	.187	6.079	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction of Married Women

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the impact of 12 variables of personal factors of married women on their job satisfaction in BPOs. From the above table it is understood that personal factors ($R = .896$), indicating a high degree of correlation among the variables ($t = 1.372, p < .01$), have a significant effect on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPOs. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of personal factors were high, the average level of job satisfaction of married women would also be high. The analysis also reveals that personal factors were able to explain the total variation in job satisfaction in BPOs by the regression model, with R^2 being about 80.2%, which is high, indicating the model fits the data well. Thus, answering the hypothesis, H1: There is a significant impact of personal factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO, posited for this research is accepted. The coefficient table shows the contribution of each personal factor to job satisfaction in BPO. From the above table, the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the

variables such as careers and their development as central concepts ($\beta=.338$)($p=.000$), traveling distance ($\beta=.193$)($p=.011$), healthy lifestyle ($\beta=.528$)($p=.000$), professional commitments ($\beta=-.240$)($p=.004$), women's demographic characteristics ($\beta=.259$)($p=.003$), ability of nurturing balance between individual and organizational ($\beta=-.169$)($p=.018$), physical health and personality skills ($\beta=-.289$)($p=.000$), and parental support ($\beta=.197$)($p=.000$) have a significant impact on the job satisfaction of working women in BPOs in Bangalore city.

Table 2: Organizational factors and job satisfaction of married women working in BPO

H0: There is no significant impact of organizational factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

H2: There is a significant impact of organizational factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.977 ^a	.954	.953	.29849		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	871.810	12	72.651	815.419	.000 ^a
	Residual	42.054	472	.089		
	Total	913.864	484			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.013	.034		.376	.707
	Job security	.237	.022	.250	10.906	.000
	Flexible time schedule	-.206	.055	-.203	-3.722	.000
	Management/Policy/Work place Support	.049	.045	.049	1.101	.272
	task autonomy/ work-role expectations	.126	.054	.123	2.346	.019
	human resource practices	.122	.046	.121	2.645	.008
	financial considerations	-.208	.049	-.211	-4.237	.000
	Leave and benefits	.205	.038	.203	5.316	.000
	safety and security of women	.202	.041	.201	4.898	.000
	change in work patterns	-.015	.034	-.015	-.434	.664
	Reduction of working time	-.023	.042	-.023	-.562	.575
	Family support initiatives	.065	.039	.065	1.684	.093
Freedom to work from home	.452	.059	.449	7.675	.000	

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction of Married Women

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the impact of 12 variables of organizational factors on job satisfaction of married women working in BPOs. From the above table it is understood that organizational factors ($R = .977$), indicating a high degree of correlation among the variables ($t = .376$, $p < .01$), have a significant effect on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPOs. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of personal factors were high, the average level of job satisfaction of married women would also be high. The analysis also reveals that organizational factors were able to explain

the total variation in job satisfaction in BPOs by the regression model, with R^2 being about 95.4%, which is high, indicating the model fits the data well. Thus, answering the hypothesis H2: There is a significant impact of organizational factors on the job satisfaction of married women working in BPO, posited for this research, is accepted. The coefficient table shows the contribution of each organizational factor to job satisfaction in BPO. From the above table, the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the variables such as job security ($\beta=.237$) ($p=.000$), flexible time schedule ($\beta=-.206$) ($p=.000$), task autonomy/work-role expectations ($\beta=.126$) ($p=.019$), human resource practices ($\beta=.122$) ($p=.008$), financial considerations ($\beta=-.208$) ($p=.000$), leave and benefits ($\beta=.205$) ($p=.000$), safety and security of women ($\beta=.202$) ($p=.000$), and freedom to work from home ($\beta=.452$) ($p=.000$) have significant impact on the job satisfaction of working women in BPOs in Bangalore city.

13. FINDINGS:

The research revealed that the unique contribution for the variables of personal factors such as careers and their development as central concepts, traveling distance, healthy lifestyle, professional commitments, women's demographic characteristics, ability to nurture balance between individual and organizational, physical health and personality skills, and parental support have a significant impact on the job satisfaction of working women in BPOs in Bangalore city.

It is also found that the unique contribution for the variables of organizational factors such as job security, flexible time schedule, task autonomy/work-role expectations, human resource practices, financial considerations, leave and benefits, safety and security of women, and freedom to work from home have a significant impact on the job satisfaction of working women in BPOs in Bangalore city.

14. SUGGESTIONS

1. To achieve a healthier work-life balance, women may need to adopt strategies such as setting clear boundaries, prioritizing tasks, seeking support from partners and family, and advocating for flexible work arrangements like remote work or adjusted hours.
2. Employers also should play a crucial role in fostering work-life balance by implementing supportive policies, such as paid parental leave, child care support, and wellness programs.
3. Most of the married women employees have no time to take care of their children and dependents, like parents and in-laws, so monthly get-togethers shall be conducted for their refreshment so that they can spend time being in the office too.
4. Reduce the workload of the married women employees by giving them only those works that they are capable of and also those targets that they can achieve in no time or less time. Like this, they can do all the work and also will have no workload.
5. Self-development activities to be conducted to enhance the married women employees more and keep every employee motivated by various activities such as on-the-job training, position enhancement, special assignments, self-directed learning projects, etc.
6. Every superior and subordinate must support the married women employee in the completion of work and also know about their expectations from the organization by providing counselling if, in case, the employee is under any pressure.
7. Leisure activities to be conducted, such as games, amusement parks, etc.

8. Since most of the married women employees want rest for two hours in the organization during their work, then fixed time should be given with various other activities, and also it should be made sure that they complete their work in the given time or before they leave from the office premises.
9. Every Saturday and Sunday to be given off, or let the employee telecommute their work so that they can spend time with their family and friends and also for self and get refreshed.
10. Advocated for the adoption of flexible work arrangements, such as remote work or staggered shifts, as a key strategy for improving work-life balance among married women in BPOs. These strategies can provide the necessary flexibility to manage household responsibilities alongside professional duties.
11. BPO companies should prioritize flexible work arrangements, including remote work options and adjustable shift timings, to help married women manage their dual responsibilities more effectively.
12. Employers can enhance support systems by providing on-site childcare, offering employee assistance programs, and encouraging shared domestic responsibilities through awareness programs.
13. Organizations should introduce wellness programs that focus on stress management, mental health, and physical well-being to address the health risks associated with work-life imbalance.
14. Providing training on time management and self-care practices can equip married women with the skills needed to balance their professional and personal lives more effectively.
15. Companies should create an inclusive and supportive work culture that acknowledges the challenges faced by married women and offers tailored solutions to help them succeed.
16. Regularly assess the effectiveness of work-life balance initiatives and make adjustments based on employee feedback and changing needs.

15. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The study deals with only two variables such as personal factors of married women and organizational factors leading to job satisfaction.
2. The study was confined to Bengaluru city alone and further confined to BPO industry only.
3. The respondents were only the married women working in BPOs.
4. The study is an opinion based survey; caution may have to be exercised while extending the result to other areas.
5. Due to time constrict only 485 number of respondents were considered.
6. The result fully on the information given by the respondents which may be based.
7. Advanced statistical tools were not used to boost up the strength for the statistical analysis.

16. DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

1. An in-depth study can be conducted on the impact of other factors leading to job satisfaction other than personal factors of married women and organizational factors.
2. There is a great scope for studying the work culture and its implication on quality of work life.
3. An in-depth study of similar nature can be conducted in IT companies in general since they share some of the distinguishing features of BPO companies.

4. A qualitative study is mooted on counselling for stress and its alleviation among the married women employees of similar nature of work.
5. Work Life Balance of the BPO married women employees and the mechanisms they use to cope can be studied in-depth.
6. A study on Role Conflict, Role Ambiguity and Role Overload of married women employees can be undertaken across other sectors as well.

17. CONCLUSION

The work-life balance among married women in the BPO sector remains a critical issue and requires concerted efforts from both employees and employers. By addressing the unique challenges women faces through flexible work arrangements, strong support systems, and organizational policies, a more equitable and sustainable work environment can be achieved. Ultimately, fostering work-life balance not only benefits individual employees but also enhances the overall productivity and job satisfaction within the BPO industry. Throughout history, women have played crucial roles in households. Nowadays, their importance in the workplace is also recognized, and they are involved in a diverse range of work activities, in addition to their routine domestic work. The study on Work life balance highlighted so many factors which will help employees balance both their professional and also personal life. When an organization frames policies as per their needs and also employee needs and expectation the proper work life balance will be maintained for all the employees working in the organization. All those factors will be very much useful for the organization to understand each employee potential in working and how to keep them motivated. This in all leads to better life and better work performance. From the study done, it is concluding that there is always a necessity for managing both work and personal life for each individual working in an organization. Further steps to be taken to improve and also provide sufficient work to every individual or employee in the organization. Steps to be taken to understand the grievances faced by the employees and what is bothering them to work insufficiently and ineffectively. Every month a get together meets with their family to be held and also to make understand their family about their work and commitments with the organization. It is very much important for an employee to take proper rest and sleep once done with work, their superior and subordinates must support them in completing them their work and also not to provide more work once they go back home.

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